

**Evaluation of Anthelmintic Potential of Aqueous and Ethanolic Leaf Extracts
of *Azadirachta indica* in Benzimidazole-Resistant
Haemonchus contortus of Sheep**

Edith, R.^{1*} and Balangatharathilagar, M.²

ISSN: 1542-2666

NAAS Rating (2025): 5.00

<https://www.jarvm.co/index.html>

jarvm.submit@gmail.com

2025; 20-1 (Part-C): 181-190

Received: 21-08-2025

Accepted: 23-09-2025

Edith, R.

¹Associate Professor, Department
of Veterinary Parasitology,
Veterinary College and Research
Institute, Salem - 636 112

Balangatharathilagar, M.

²Professor, Department of Clinics,
Madras Veterinary College,
Chennai-600 007
Tamil Nadu Veterinary and Animal
Sciences University

***Corresponding author:**

Edith, R.

¹Associate Professor, Department
of Veterinary Parasitology,
Veterinary College and Research
Institute, Salem - 636 112

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17185240

Abstract

This study aimed to evaluate the anthelmintic potential of aqueous leaf extract of *Azadirachta indica* against benzimidazole-resistant *Haemonchus contortus* of sheep. A faecal egg count reduction test (FECRT) was conducted in organized sheep farms in Salem, Karur, Kanniyakumari, Kancheepuram and Thiruvallur districts of Tamil Nadu using fenbendazole. 560 dung samples collected from the above sheep farms were subjected to coprological examination revealed *Haemonchus contortus* eggs. FECRT and allele-specific PCR (AS-PCR) confirmed the benzimidazole resistance in samples from Kancheepuram and Thiruvallur districts. Aqueous and ethanolic leaf extracts of *A. indica* at different concentrations viz., 0.5, 1, 2 and 5 per cent, were tested against resistant *H. contortus* of sheep reared in these farms with BZ resistance. The maximum of 35.42±1.87% inhibition of egg hatch was observed in 5% aqueous leaf extracts (ALE) of *A. indica* compared to 26.67±1.23 % inhibition of egg hatch in ethanolic leaf extract (ELE). The maximum mean larval paralysis observed in 5 % ALE and ELE of *A. indica* were 28.89±1.11% and 26.67±1.23 % respectively at 60 min. It was observed that increased concentration of extracts resulted in increased efficacy of inhibition on egg hatch and mean larval paralysis. It is concluded that *A. indica* could be a promising phytomedicine for the benzimidazole-resistant nematodes of sheep.

Key words: Sheep, *Haemonchus contortus*, Neem, *Azadirachta indica*, aqueous leaf extract, ethanolic leaf extract, Benzimidazole, anthelmintic resistance

Introduction

Anthelmintic resistance poses a threat to the sheep industry in terms of reduced performance and failure to control clinical disease on a global basis. The nematode parasites of sheep viz., *Trichostrongyles* sp., *Haemonchus contortus*, and *Teladorsagia circumcincta* have been reported to have developed benzimidazole resistance by single nucleotide polymorphism (SNP). Under intensive systems of animal management, most worm control strategies currently rely heavily on the use of anthelmintics. However, the regular use of any chemical to control infectious organisms poses the risk of developing resistant populations. Worldwide reports of nematodes with resistance to one or more of the available broad-spectrum anthelmintic groups are therefore of great concern to all of those involved in advising on parasite control. To maintain the production benefits of intensive livestock production systems, the efficacy of available compounds must be maintained so that worm control measures remain effective. When all the available compounds have been exhausted, there are at least chances of finding alternate compounds in the form of botanical or herbal anthelmintics in India. Reports documented the usage of many plant materials for treating animal diseases, especially against the gastrointestinal parasites of ruminants viz., *Pithecellobium dulce*, *Momordica charantia*, *Carica papaya*, *Melia azedarach*, *Azadirachta indica*, *Moringa olifera*, *Vitex negundo* and Oyster mushrooms (Rastogi et al., 2009; Edith et al., 2022; Edith et al., 2023; Khan et al., 2024)

Neem (*Azadirachta indica*) is known as the “village pharmacy.” The National Academies Press (the publishing arm of the US Academy of Science) published a book in 1992 titled, *Neem: A Tree for Solving Global Problems*. Its description says, “The neem tree, one of the most promising of all plants, may eventually benefit every person on the planet. Probably no other

plant yields as many varied products or has as many exploitable by-products. Several reports reviewed the pharmacological activities of *A. indica* (Maithani et al., 2011; Dubey and Kashyap, 2014; Uzzaman, 2020).

Various parts of the neem have been used as an anthelmintic in livestock viz., leaves (Costa et al., 2006; Chagas et al., 2008; Dongre et al., 2014; Jamra et al., 2015), seed (Iqbal et al., 2010), aqueous, ethanolic and methanolic extracts of leaves (Priscilla et al., 2014; Agarwal and Bagai, 2014; Nawaz et al., 2014; Agarwal et al., 2016; Gadhave et al., 2019; Rehman et al., 2023; Hawsah et al., 2023; Adams et al., 2023), root and stems (Yakuba et al., 2006) and essential oils (Jeyathilakan et al., 2010; Batool et al., 2023). The above studies have investigated the anthelmintic potential of *A. indica* against helminth parasites. The knowledge gap was recognized in the potential of neem leaves of *A. indica* on benzimidazole-resistant *H. contortus*. Hence, this study was conducted to evaluate the anthelmintic potential of *A. indica* on benzimidazole-resistant *H. contortus*.

Materials and Methods

Collection and processing of the plant:

A. indica leaves were collected from fields of Salem, Karur, Kancheepuram and Thiruvallur districts. The leaves were thoroughly washed in water. Then they were shadow-dried in the open. After complete drying, leaves were ground using an electric blender to make into powder. The powder was stored in airtight containers until further use (Fig. 1a and 1b)

Preparation of aqueous and ethanolic leaf extracts of *A. indica*:

The aqueous leaf extract (ALE) of *A. indica*, four hundred grams of leaf powder was macerated using one litre of water for 48 hours at room temperature with intermittent stirring. For the ethanolic extract (ELE) of *A. indica*, four hundred grams of leaf powder was macerated using one litre of ethanol for 48 hours at room

temperature with intermittent stirring. After maceration, double filtration was done using muslin cloth and Whatman No. 1 filter paper. The filtrates obtained were evaporated using an incubator. Dried extracts were labelled and stored at -20 °C until further use.

Detection of Anthelmintic Resistance:

Anthelmintic resistance was detected by using *in vivo* faecal egg count reduction test, allele-specific polymerase chain reaction, *in vitro* Egg hatch assay and larval paralysis assay.

1. Faecal Egg Count Reduction Test (FECRT):

This is the most common *in vivo* test to detect Anthelmintic Resistance. This test provides an estimation of anthelmintic efficacy by comparing faecal egg counts of animals before and after treatment.

The sheep in the organized farms from Karur, Melmaruvathur, Nagercoil, Salem, Kancheepuram and Thiruvallur treated with oral fenbendazole at a standard dose rate of 7.5 mg/Kg body weight and the dung samples were collected on 0, 7 and 14 days post-treatment.

The collected dung samples were packed in polythene bags with the air excluded and sealed. In this study, care was taken to transport the dung samples and store them in the laboratory at 4°C before being subjected to Egg Per Gram (EPG), egg hatch assay and larval paralysis assay as quickly as possible.

Egg Per Gram (EPG) was calculated using Mc Master Method. Briefly, four grams of dung sample was mixed with 26 ml of tap water and homogenised. The homogenized suspension was filtered through a sieve. The filtrate was collected and centrifuged at 2000 rpm for 2 minutes. The supernatant was poured off. 26 ml of saturated salt solution was added to the sediment and agitated. This suspension was loaded into a three-chambered McMaster slide chamber. Samples from different places were loaded separately in each chamber of Mc Master Slide. EPG was calculated by multiplying the number of eggs counted by 25.

2. Detection of benzimidazole resistance by allele-specific PCR:

Eggs separated from dung samples were used for DNA extraction using a commercial stool DNA extraction Kit.

Amplification of β -tubulin was done in a final volume of 25 μ l using primers Pn1- 5' GGC AAA TAT GTC CCA CGT GC3' and Pn2- 5' GAT CAG CAT TCA GCT GTC CA3', each 1.5 μ l, 12.5 μ l Red dye mix, 7.0 μ l DNA template and 2.5 μ l of nuclease-free water. PCR reaction was carried out on a gradient thermo cycler (Eppendorf) with initial denaturation at 94°C for 3 min, followed by 36 cycles (denaturation 94°C for 55 sec, annealing 57°C for 55 sec and extension 72°C for 55 sec) with the final extension at 72°C for 10 min and the PCR products were visualized after gel electrophoresis using Gel Doc system.

Nested PCR was performed using amplicons of β tubulin as DNA template in a final volume of 25 μ l with primers (10 pm/ μ l) F Pn3-GGA ACA ATG GAC TCT GTT CG 3' and R Pn4-GGG AAT CGA AGG CAG GTC GT 3' each 1.5 μ l, 12.5 μ l Red dye mix, 3.0 μ l DNA Template and 6.5 μ l nuclease free water. PCR reaction was carried out on a Gradient Thermo cycler. PCR cyclic profiles and visualization were similar to β tubulin amplification.

Coproculture revealed predominantly *Haemonchus contortus* larvae. Hence this allele-specific PCR was done to detect the resistant and susceptible alleles of *H. contortus*. Reaction was performed using different sets of primers for resistant and susceptible alleles.

Amplicons of Nested PCR were used as a DNA template for this allele-specific PCR with the following published primer sequences (Silvestre and Humbert, 2000).

Ph1-5' GGA ACG ATG GAC TCC TTT CG 3'

Ph2-5' GAT CAG CAT TCA GCT GTC CA 3'

Ph3-5' CTG GTA GAG AAC ACC GAT GAA
ACA TA 3'

Ph4-5' ATA CATG AGC TTC GTT GTC AAT
ACA GA 3'

The reaction was performed in a total volume of 25 µl using a Gradient thermo cycler. Cyclic conditions are similar to those of beta-tubulin amplification.

PCR products were visualized by submarine gel electrophoresis and staining with ethidium bromide. Briefly, the ladder was reconstituted with deionised water, 6X gel loading dye and 200- 2000bp DNA ladder, respectively in the ratio of 4: 1: 1. A two per cent agarose gel was prepared by dissolving one g of agarose in 50 ml of 0.5X TBE buffer. One µl of ethidium bromide working solution was added to give a final concentration of 0.5 µg of ethidium bromide per ml of the gel. Gel was cast in UV UV-transparent submarine gel electrophoresis system (Broviga), and wells were prepared by placing a comb at one end. After complete setting of the gel, the comb was removed and 0.5X TBE buffer was poured to cover the gel.

Ten microlitres of the amplicons were mixed with 2 µl of gel loading dye and loaded into the wells. Three µl of 200-2000bp DNA ladder was included in each run. Electrophoresis was carried out at a constant voltage of 85 V. The products were visualized and photographed using a video gel documentation system (BIO RAD Gel Doc XR+).

3. Assessment of resistance by egg hatch assay (EHA):

The Egg Hatch Assay method is an *in vitro* diagnostic method of Anthelmintic Resistance. This provides an accurate method for assessing the susceptibility of mixed nematode populations also and it is more rapid and economic test. This test is based on the determination of the proportion of eggs that fail to hatch in solutions of increasing drug concentrations in relation to control wells.

i. Preparation of working solutions of ALE:

Aqueous leaf extract powder of *A. indica* was dissolved in distilled water to prepare the final concentration of 0.5%, 1%, 2% and 5% in the 24-well plate.

ii. Preparation of working solutions of ELE:

Ethanollic leaf extract powder of *A. indica* was dissolved in dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) to prepare the final concentration of 0.5%, 1%, 2% and 5% in the 24-well plate.

iii. Preparation of Thiabendazole (TBZ) stock and working solutions:

Pure thiabendazole (Sigma-T-8904) 50mg was transferred into a 50 ml beaker, and 50ml of dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) was added and mixed thoroughly to prepare a stock solution of 1000 ppm of thiabendazole. Using the stock solution, a suitable range of working solutions was prepared to a final concentration of 0.1, 0.2, 0.3 µg/ml.

The method described by Lourderaj (2005) was followed for the egg hatch assay with minor modifications. Briefly, to each well of a 24 multiwell plate, 500µl of egg suspension containing approximately 40 eggs was added. 500 µl of working solution of 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, µg/ml TBZ was added to each benzimidazole control wells. 500µl of aqueous leaf extract of *A. indica* was added with a final concentration of 0.5%, 1%, 2% & 5% in different wells. 500 µl of DMSO (99 per cent) was added to the negative control wells. The tests were carried out with six

replicates for each drug concentration and controls. The volume in each well was made up to 2 ml using distilled water. The plate was incubated at 25^o C for 48 hours. After incubation, one drop of Lugol's iodine was added to stop further embryonation of eggs.

The mean number of eggs and larvae at each concentration of TBZ was counted under a binocular stereo zoom microscope (Olympus SZ40, Japan) and percentage of hatch was derived using the following formula to determine the resistance status. The percentage hatch was taken as a percentage of resistance as the larvae survived anthelmintic treatment.

$$\text{Percentage hatch} = \frac{\text{Number of larvae hatched}}{\text{Total number of eggs added}} \times 100$$

After 48 hrs, the number of eggs embryonated and unembryonated was counted under a binocular stereo zoom microscope (Olympus SZ40, Japan). The percentage of unembryonated eggs was calculated to determine the susceptibility of the extracts used.

Thus, the percentage efficacy of aqueous and ethanolic leaf extracts of *A. indica* was assessed to tackle resistance.

4. Larval Paralysis Assay (LPA):

This assay discriminates between resistant and susceptible strains of parasites by estimating the proportion of third-stage larvae in tonic paralysis after incubation with increasing drug concentrations. To test the effect of aqueous extracts of *A. indica* on larval paralysis, this assay was performed using ivermectin as a standard positive control.

Briefly, in a 24-well multiplate 500 µL of an aqueous leaf extract of *A. indica* was added at final concentrations of 0.5%, 1%, 2% & 5% in

each well. 500 µl of 0.9µg/ml concentration of ivermectin was taken as a standard positive control, and water was taken as a negative control. 500µl of larval suspension containing approximately 30 larvae was added to each well. The mobile and immobile larval counts were taken at 15-minute intervals for a 60-minute duration at room temperature. Paralysed larvae were counted and expressed as a percentage.

Results

1. Faecal egg count reduction test (FECRT)

EPG on 0 and 14-day samples was calculated using McMaster, and assessment of development of resistance was calculated using RESO 4.0 software. FCERT was carried out in 560 sheep from organized sheep farms of Salem, Karur, Nagercoil, Melmaruvathur, Kancheepuram and Thiruvallur for the development of resistance to benzimidazole. A reduction of faecal egg count less than 95% or the lower 95% confidence limit less than 90% was considered as resistance, and if any of the above parameters were not met, then it was classified as suspected resistance. In this study, out of 560 samples tested, 106 samples from Kancheepuram and Thiruvallur districts showed resistance, and the remaining 454 samples were susceptible to Benzimidazole.

2. Allele-specific PCR (AS-PCR)

Allele-specific PCR was performed based on the method of Silvestre and Humbert (2000). In this resistant fragment size of 250 BP could be obtained (Fig. 2). Development of resistance could be detected both by FECRT and also AS-PCR for samples from organized sheep farms of Kancheepuram and Thiruvallur districts.

Lane-8,10,12,14,16- 250bp- Resistance ; Lane- 9,13,15,17- 770 bp- β tubulin

Fig.2 AS-PCR showing amplification of the resistant gene (rr)

3. Egg Hatch Assay

The egg hatch assay was used to test the efficacy of the aqueous leaf extract of *A. indica*. The results of the Egg Hatch Assay are presented in Table 1.

Table.1 Efficacy of Aqueous and Ethanolic Leaf Extracts of *A. indica* in EHA

Concentrations of <i>A.indica</i> leaf extracts and TBZ	Per cent inhibition of egg hatch			
ALE /ELE concentrations	0.5%	1%	2%	5%
ALE	1.83±1.05 ^a	3.33± 0.86 ^{ab}	22.08±1.50 ^c	35.42±1.87 ^d
ELE	4.44±1.41 ^a	15.00±0.91 ^b	20.00±1.44 ^c	26.67±1.23 ^d
TBZ concentrations	0	0.1 µg/ml	0.2 µg/ml	0.3 µg/ml
TBZ	1.66±0.74 ^a	35.563±2.22 ^b	42.223±2.05 ^c	53.89±3.59 ^d

^{a,b,c} Mean values with different superscripts differ significantly (P< 0.05%)

The results show that there was significant inhibition of egg hatch by different concentrations of aqueous leaf extract of *A. indica* after 48 hours of incubation. 5% aqueous leaf extract of *A. indica* showed 11.67 % inhibition of egg hatch.

4. Larval Paralysis Assay

The results of Larval Paralysis are presented in Table.2 and 3

Table 2. Mean larval paralysis in aqueous leaf extract (ALE) of *A. indica*

Time	PBS	Concentration of aqueous leaf extract of <i>A. indica</i>				Ivermectin (0.03 µg/ml)
		0.5%	1%	2%	5%	
15 Min	0	0	4.44 ± 0.70 ^a	7.22±1.02 ^a	13.89±1.03 ^a	83.89±5.24
30 Min	0	0	7.78± 0.70 ^b	11.67±1.14 ^b	17.78±1.41 ^b	98.33±2.87
45 Min	0	0	11.11±1.41 ^c	18.89±1.11 ^c	23.33±1.49 ^c	100±0
60 Min	0	0	14.99±1.14 ^d	19.45±1.02 ^c	28.89±1.11 ^d	100±0

^{a,b,c} Mean values with different superscripts differ significantly (P< 0.05%)

Table 3. Larval Paralysis Assay in the ethanolic leaf extract (ELE) of *A. indica*

Time	PBS	Concentration of EthanolicNeem Extract				Ivermectin (0.03 µg/ml)
		0.5%	1%	2%	5%	
15 Min	0	0	0.55±0.55 ^a	1.11±0.70 ^a	4.44±0.70 ^a	83.89±5.24
30 Min	0	0	0.55±0.55 ^a	3.89±1.02 ^a	8.89±1.11 ^b	98.33±2.87
45 Min	0	0	3.89±1.03 ^b	7.78±1.04 ^b	9.45±1.02 ^b	100±0
60 Min	0	0	3.89±1.03 ^b	8.33±1.43 ^b	10.56±1.59 ^b	100±0

The LPA revealed that an increased percentage of paralysis occurred as the concentration of aqueous and ethanolic leaf extracts of *A. indica* was increased from 0.5% to 5%. The maximum paralysis was observed in 5% concentration of ALE and ELE of *A. indica* were 28.89±1.11% and 26.67±1.23 % respectively, at 60 min.

Discussion

The FECRT provides an estimation of anthelmintic efficacy by comparing faecal egg counts of animals before and after treatment (Boersema, 1983; Presidente, 1985). The guidelines that give precise details and recommendations on the use of the FECRT have been used in this study (Coles *et al.*, 1992).

Benzimidazole drugs selectively bind to β -tubulins of the parasitic nematodes, resulting in inhibition of microtubule formation. The insoluble polymeric microtubules are formed from soluble alpha- and beta-tubulin molecules. The microtubules of nematode parasites play vital cell functions like cell division, shaping, motility and intracellular substrate transport. Genetic analysis reports revealed that beta-tubulin polymorphism at codons 167 and 200 of the beta-tubulin isotype-1 led to changes in the amino acid sequence, resulting in the expression of tyrosine in resistant worms instead of phenylalanine in susceptible worms, where benzimidazole binds between the beta-tubulin phenylalanine residues at 167 and 200.

Egg hatch assay was used to assess the resistance to thiabendazole in this study. The egg hatch assay is fast, inexpensive, sensitive and repeatable when a single species of nematode is involved in resistance (Prichard *et al.*, 1980). In this study, the assessment of resistance to thiabendazole in *H. contortus* was done. The mean percentage of egg hatch in one hundred and six resistant samples was above the

discriminating dose of 0.1 µg per ml of TBZ and larvae hatched even at higher concentration of TBZ i.e 0.3 µg per ml of TBZ. This is similar to the report of Le Jambre (1976) reported that TBZ-resistant strains hatched in higher concentrations of TBZ than non-resistant strains. Coles *et al.* (1992) reported for the first time that eggs with an ED₅₀ value in excess of 0.1 µg TBZ per ml were indicative of benzimidazole resistance. Taylor *et al.* (2002) reported eggs from susceptible individuals rarely hatched at concentrations greater than 0.1µg / ml of thiabendazole.

In Tamil Nadu, Lourderaj (2005) reported the development of resistance in the nematode parasites of sheep with the ED₅₀ values of 0.8 and 0.6 µg TBZ per ml in Erode and Othiawakam. Easwaran *et al.* (2009) reported benzimidazole resistance in gastrointestinal nematodes of sheep in three farms of southern India with the ED₅₀ values of 0.627, 0.678 and 0.388 µg / ml of TBZ. The assessment of resistance by EHA in this study was on similar lines and in agreement with the earlier reports from Tamil Nadu.

The leaf extracts of *A. indica* were found to be effective in dose-dependent manner. The highest dose (25mg/mL) of methanolic and ethyl acetate extract allowed hatching of only 1.12 and 3.57% of eggs (Rehman *et al.*, 2023). *In vivo* studies revealed a significant reduction in faecal egg count in goats (Priscilla *et al.*, 2014; Dongre *et al.*, 2014) and cattle (Jamra *et al.*, 2015) treated with *A. indica* leaf powder and leaf extracts.

The larval paralysis test was developed for the detection of levamisole and morantel resistance (Martin and LeJambre, 1979). In the assay, infective third-stage larvae were incubated for one hour in serial dilutions of the anthelmintic for 60 min and after this time, the percentage of paralysed larvae was determined at each concentration, and a dose-response line is plotted and compared to a known anthelmintic. The present study revealed that aqueous leaf extract of *A. indica* has the potential anthelmintic property in worms that were resistant to benzimidazole. The *A. indica* leaves reported to have 20 phyto compounds based on the peaks identified by Gas chromatography- Mass Spectroscopy with a molecular weight ranging from 144 to 336 with higher levels of oleic acid, nanodecanoic acid, octadecanoic acid and arabinopyranoside (Adams *et al.*, 2023).

5. Conclusions

A total of 560 dung samples from organized sheep farms of Salem, Karur, Kanniyakumari, Kancheepuram and Thiruvallur districts of Tamil Nadu was examined by FECRT for development of resistance to benzimidazole. The samples from Kancheepuram and Thiruvallur districts showed resistance to benzimidazole by FECRT. The allele-specific PCR (AS-PCR) also confirmed the benzimidazole resistance in samples from Kancheepuram and Thiruvallur districts. The aqueous and ethanolic leaf extracts of *A. indica* were tested against benzimidazole-resistant strongyle nematodes of sheep reared in these farms. The maximum inhibition of egg hatch was noticed in 5% aqueous leaf extracts of *A. indica* (35.42±1.87 %) compared to other extracts. The maximum mean larval paralysis observed was 28.89±1.11% in 5 % aqueous extract at 60 min. It was observed that increased concentration of extracts resulted in increased efficacy of inhibition on egg hatch and mean larval paralysis. It is concluded that *A. indica* could be a promising phytomedicine for the benzimidazole-

resistant nematodes of sheep. There is ample scope for further exploration of *A. indica* as an alternative phytomedicine to combat anthelmintic resistance in livestock.

References:

1. Adams, E. G., Ekott, E. J., Usip, L. P., & Opara, K. N. (2023). Efficacy of *Azadirachta indica* in the Treatment of Gastrointestinal Helminthiasis. *Biotechnology Journal International*, 27(2), 47-55.
2. Aggarwal, R., & Bagai, U. (2014). Evaluation of anthelmintic activity of ethanolic and aqueous leaf extracts of *Azadirachta indica* on phosphatases in *Gastrothylax indicus*. *IOSR Journal of Pharmacy and Biological Sciences (IOSR-JPBS)*, 9, 98-104.
3. Aggarwal, R., Kaur, K., Suri, M., & Bagai, U. (2016). Anthelmintic potential of *Calotropis procera*, *Azadirachta indica* and *Punica granatum* against *Gastrothylax indicus*. *Journal of parasitic diseases*, 40(4), 1230-1238.
4. Batool, S., Munir, F., Sindhu, Z.U.D., Abbas, R.Z., Aslam, B., Khan, M.K., Imran, M., Aslam, M.A., Ahmad, M. and Chaudhary, M.K., 2023. *In vitro* anthelmintic activity of *Azadirachta indica* (Neem) and *Melia azedarach* (Bakain) essential oils and their silver nanoparticles against *Haemonchus contortus*. *Agrobiological Records* 11:6-12.
5. Boersema, J. H. (1983). Possibilities and limitations in the detection of anthelmintic resistance. Facts and reflections IV. Resistance of parasites to anthelmintics. A workshop in the C.E.C. animal pathology programme held at the Central Veterinary Institute, Lelystad, The Netherlands, 9-10 December 1982. 207-215
6. Chagas, A. C. S., Vieira, L. S., Freitas, A. R., Araújo, M. R. A., Araújo-Filho, J. A., Araguaio, W. R., & Navarro, A. M. C. (2008). Anthelmintic efficacy of neem (*Azadirachta*

- indica* A. Juss) and the homeopathic product Fator Vermes® in Morada Nova sheep. *Veterinary Parasitology*, 151(1), 68-73.
7. Coles, G. C., Bauer, C., Borgsteede, F. H. M., Geerts, S., Klei, T. R., Taylor, M. A., & Waller, P. J. (1992). World Association for the Advancement of Veterinary Parasitology (WAAVP) methods for the detection of anthelmintic resistance in nematodes of veterinary importance. *Veterinary parasitology*, 44(1-2), 35-44.
 8. Costa, C. T. C., Bevilaqua, C. M. L., Maciel, M. V., Camurça-Vasconcelos, A. L. F., Morais, S. M., Monteiro, M. V. B., ... & Souza, M. M. C. (2006). Anthelmintic activity of *Azadirachta indica* A. Juss against sheep gastrointestinal nematodes. *Veterinary parasitology*, 137(3-4), 306-310.
 9. Dongre, S., Das, G., Nath, S., Dixit, A. K., & Agrawal, V. (2015). Anthelmintic efficacy of *Azadirachta indica* (neem) against strongyles in goats. *The Indian Journal of Veterinary Sciences and Biotechnology*, 10(3), 18-21.
 10. Dubey, S., & Kashyap, P. (2014). *Azadirachta indica*: a plant with versatile potential. *RGUHS J Pharm Sci*, 4(2), 39-46.
 11. Easwaran, C., Jeyagopal Harikrishnan, T., & Raman, M. (2009). Multiple anthelmintic resistance in gastrointestinal nematodes of sheep in Southern India. *Veterinarski arhiv*, 79(6), 611-620.
 12. Edith, R., Latha, B.R. and Balagangatharathilagar, M. (2022). Evaluation of anthelmintic efficacy of *Pithecellobium dulce*, *Momordica charantia* and *Carica papaya* leaf extracts on egg hatching and larval development of *Haemonchus contortus*. *The Pharma Innovation Journal*, 11(12): 3743-3748
 13. Edith, R., Meignanalakshmi, S., Vijayarani, K. and M.Balagangatharathilagar, M. (2023). *In vitro* evaluation of antiparasitic activity of oyster mushroom (*Pleurotus ostreatus*) protein hydrolysates against *Haemonchus contortus* larvae. *The Pharma Innovation Journal*. 2023;12(3):5882- 85.
 14. Gadhawe, A. M., Karande, V. V., Ghumare, B. C., Kundu, K., Jadhav, S. N., & Mhase, P. P. (2019). Evaluation of anthelmintic efficacy of ethanolic extract of *Azadirachta indica* in goats. *Int. J. Pure Appl. Biosci*, 7, 568-573.
 15. Hawsah, M. A., Abdel-Gaber, R., Al-Quraishy, S., Aljawdah, H. M., Maodaa, S. N., & Al-Shaebi, E. (2023). Green synthesis of selenium nanoparticles using *Azadirachta indica* leaves extract: evaluation of anthelmintic and biocompatibility potential. *Food Science and Technology*, 43.
 16. Iqbal, Z., Lateef, M., Jabbar, A., & Gilani, A. H. (2010). *In vivo* anthelmintic activity of *Azadirachta indica* A. Juss seeds against gastrointestinal nematodes of sheep. *Veterinary parasitology*, 168(3-4), 342-345.
 17. Jamra, N., Das, G., Singh, P., & Haque, M. (2015). Anthelmintic efficacy of crude neem (*Azadirachta indica*) leaf powder against bovine strongylosis. *Journal of parasitic diseases*, 39(4), 786-788.
 18. Jeyathilakan, N., Murali, K., Anandaraj, A., Latha, B. R., & Basith, S. A. (2010). Anthelmintic activity of essential oils of *Cymbopogon nardus* and *Azadirachta indica* on *Fasciola gigantica*. *J Vet Animal Sci*, 6(6), 204-9.
 19. Khan, F. A., Swarnkar, C. P., Soni, L. K., & Sharma, S. R. (2024). Phytochemicals, antioxidant ability and *in vitro* anthelmintic activity of crude extracts from *Vitex negundo* leaves against *Haemonchus contortus*. *Journal of Parasitic Diseases*, 48(2), 257-268.
 20. Le Jambre, L. F. (1976). Egg hatch as an *in vitro* assay of thiabendazole resistance in nematodes. *Veterinary Parasitology*, 2(4), 385-391.

21. Lourderaj, I. 2005. Evaluation of detection methods of anthelmintic resistance in *Haemonchus contortus*. M.V.Sc., Thesis submitted to Tamil Nadu Veterinary and Animal Sciences University, Chennai-51.
22. Maithani, A., Parcha, V., Pant, G., Dhulia, I., & Kumar, D. (2011). *Azadirachta indica* (neem) leaf: A review. *J Pharm Res*, 4(6), 1824-1827.
23. Martin, P. J., & Le Jambre, L. F. (1979). Larval paralysis as an in vitro assay of levamisole and morantel tartrate resistance in *Ostertagia*. *Veterinary Science Communications*, 3(1), 159-164.
24. Nawaz, M., Sajid, S. M., Zubair, M., Hussain, J., Abbasi, Z., Mohi-Ud-Din, A., & Waqas, M. (2014). *In vitro* and *in vivo* anthelmintic activity of leaves of *Azadirachta indica*, *Dalbergia sisso* and *Morus alba* against *Haemonchus contortus*. *Glob. Vet*, 13(6), 996-1001.
25. Presidente, P.J.A., 1985. Methods for detection of resistance to anthelmintics. In: Resistance in Nematodes to Anthelmintics, CSIRO Division of Animal Health, Glebe NSW, Australia, p. 15.
26. Prichard, R. K., Hall, C. A., Kelly, J. D., Martin, I. C. A., & Donald, A. D. (1980). The problem of anthelmintic resistance in nematodes.
27. Priscilla, F. X., Amin, M. R., & Rahman, S. (2014). Comparative study of neem (*Azadirachta indica*), bitter gourd (*Momordica charantia*) extract as herbal anthelmintic and albendazole as chemical anthelmintic in controlling gastrointestinal nematodes in goats. *IOSR Journal of Agriculture and Veterinary Science*, 7(2), 33-37.
28. Rastogi T, Bhutda V, Moon K, Aswar, P.B., and Khadabadi, S.S. (2009). Comparative studies on anthelmintic activity of *Moringa oleifera* and *Vitex negundo*. *Asian Journal of Research in chemistry*. 2009 2(2), 181-182.
29. Rehman, G., Umar, M., Shah, N., Hamayun, M., Ali, A., Khan, W. and Ali, S. (2023). Green synthesis and characterization of silver nanoparticles using *Azadirachta indica* seeds extract: *in vitro* and *in vivo* evaluation of anti-diabetic activity. *Pharmaceuticals*, 16(12), 1677.
30. Silvestre, A., & Humbert, J. F. (2000). A molecular tool for species identification and benzimidazole resistance diagnosis in larval communities of small ruminant parasites. *Experimental Parasitology*, 95(4), 271-276.
31. Taylor, M. A., Hunt, K. R., & Goodyear, K. L. (2002). Anthelmintic resistance detection methods. *Veterinary parasitology*, 103(3), 183-194.
32. Uzzaman, S. (2020). Pharmacological activities of neem (*Azadirachta indica*): A review. *Int. J. Pharmacogn. Life Sci*, 1(1), 38-41.
33. Yakubu, S., Saleh, U. A., & Abdullahi, G. (2006). In-vitro anthelmintic efficacy of crude aqueous extracts of neem (*Azadirachta indica*) leaf, stem and root on nematode. *Animal Research International*, 3(3), 549-552.